

Improving Solar Energy Harvesting in Concentrated Photovoltaic-Thermal Systems Using Dual-Axis Tracking Mirrors

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Abstract—The deployment of hybrid solar energy systems, particularly concentrated photovoltaic-thermal (CPV-T) systems capable of simultaneously generating electrical and thermal energy, has attracted increasing attention due to their potential for enhanced efficiency. Among the various strategies investigated to enhance system performance, dynamically controlled concentrating mirrors, such as heliostats, have demonstrated exceptional effectiveness. This study examines the impact of dual-axis sun-tracking mirrors on CPV-T efficiency under real-time operational conditions. The proposed system integrates three coaxial mirrors mounted on two motorized axes, enabling continuous and precise sun tracking through adjustments of both vertical and horizontal angles to optimize solar radiation capture. The system employs an open-loop controller to drive the motorized axes, ensuring accurate mirror alignment without the need for feedback sensors. By employing movable mirrors, the stationary photovoltaic-thermal (PV-T) device benefits from sustained exposure to solar irradiance and precise alignment of all three mirrors towards the PV-T module, leading to significant performance improvements. Experimental findings confirm that this dynamic tracking mechanism, driven by the open-loop controller, enhances system efficiency, highlighting its potential for advancing CPV-T technology.

Index Terms—Concentrated photovoltaic-thermal, power efficiency, sun-tracking.

I. INTRODUCTION

CONCENTRATED photovoltaic thermal (CPV-T) systems integrate photovoltaic and thermal technologies to concurrently produce electricity and useful heat from concentrated sunlight. This dual-energy conversion approach significantly enhances overall efficiency and optimizes land use, making CPV-T systems both economically attractive and environmentally sustainable. CPV-T technology presents a promising solution to support the global transition toward solar energy

by achieving higher energy yields in a reduced footprint. Its adaptability to diverse environmental conditions further underscores its potential as a sustainable and scalable power generation technology [1]–[3].

This study aims to address key technical challenges in CPV-T systems and contribute to their performance optimization. By integrating advanced technologies such as sun trackers, hybrid photovoltaic-thermal panels, and mirror reflectors, CPV-T systems offer a highly efficient and adaptable solution for sustainable energy generation. Their ability to operate effectively across diverse environmental conditions reinforces their potential in supporting the global transition toward renewable energy [4].

Recent advancements in solar tracking and CPV-T systems highlight the critical role of optical optimization and thermal management in enhancing overall efficiency. Dual-axis solar tracking has been shown to significantly improve energy yield by maintaining optimal irradiance angles [5]. The integration of reflective mirrors with trough systems has demonstrated substantial gains in concentrated solar flux distribution [6]. Hybrid approaches that combine dynamic tracking with active cooling strategies, such as those explored by [7], further emphasize the synergy between optical precision and thermal regulation in CPV-T systems. The thermal performance of CPV-T systems is highly sensitive to geometric and operational parameters, as highlighted in parametric studies of absorber configurations [8]. Long-term reliability remains a key concern, particularly for tracking systems exposed to environmental stressors, necessitating robust mechanical designs and durable materials [9]. Recent advancements in adaptive control algorithms, including machine learning (ML)-driven tracking optimization [10], [11], present promising avenues for real-time performance tuning. Building on these developments,

this study investigates the synergistic effects of solar tracking mirrors on CPV-T efficiency, with a focus on mitigating optical losses and thermal degradation while addressing scalability challenges identified in prior research.

Several studies have explored the impact of tracking accuracy on system performance. Badescu et al. [12] analyzed heliostat tracking errors and their influence on concentrated radiation distribution, comparing empirical probability distribution models such as Gaussian and Uniform Distribution Approaches with measurement data from [13]. In a related study, [14] developed an algorithm for residual aberration analysis in non-imaging focusing heliostats, which enhances optical accuracy. Moeller et al. [15] introduced a control strategy for detecting cloud passages, enabling heliostats to transition to a standby position and automatically resume their original orientation after cloud cover dissipates.

Further advancements in sun-tracking technologies have focused on improving precision and adaptability. Aiuchi et al. [13] designed, constructed, and tested a photo-sensor-based sun-tracking system using an equatorial mount and auxiliary sensors, achieving a sun-tracking error of 0.6 mrad in clear weather. The tracking accuracy diminished under cloudy conditions, resulting in increased energy losses. Kirbus et al. [16] tested a closed-loop control system at the Weizmann Institute heliostat field, which dynamically corrected tracking errors by detecting spillage, measuring aiming errors, and applying feedback corrections. This system achieved a remarkable precision of 0.1 mrad.

This paper presents a novel structural design for a practical mirror-integrated CPV-T system. The proposed system features a dual-axis solar tracking mechanism equipped with three movable mirrors, strategically angled to reflect direct, diffuse, and reflected solar radiation. These mirrors are dynamically controlled by two motors, enabling precise tracking of the sun's trajectory. This configuration optimizes and amplifies sunlight concentration onto a stationary PV-T system, significantly enhancing thermal energy generation while simultaneously boosting electrical output.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces the system description, including the hybrid photovoltaic-thermal panel, and the storage system, followed by the remote data acquisition, monitoring, and control platform. Section II focuses also on the triple sun-tracking mirror system, discussing its operational principles, geometric configuration, and shadow-casting analysis. Section III details the implementation of the open-loop controller, presenting the mathematical formulations for mirror orientation, motor control strategies, and the overall tracking mechanism. Section IV presents the experimental results, analyzing system performance under real-world conditions and evaluating the impact of the tracking mechanism on thermal and electrical efficiency. Finally, Section V concludes the paper by summarizing the key findings, addressing potential improvements, and outlining future research directions.

Fig. 1. Key components of the CPV-T system located in Granges, Valais, Switzerland, including the triple sun-tracking mirrors, stationary PV-T, PLC with its I/O modules, sensors, actuators, and a water tank.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

This section introduces the integrated concentrated photovoltaic-thermal system equipped with a Beckhoff PLC for monitoring and control. The system features a dual-axis solar tracking mechanism and strategically positioned concentrating mirrors to maximize sunlight reflection onto a stationary photovoltaic-thermal panel, thereby improving both thermal and electrical power output. The CPV-T system comprises three adjustable mirrors mounted on a dual-axis tracking platform. These mirrors are designed to redirect reflected solar radiation onto the stationary hybrid PV-T panel. The system utilizes two motorized actuators that continuously adjust the mirrors' orientation based on the sun's azimuth and zenith angles throughout the day, thereby maximizing solar energy capture and enhancing overall efficiency. Fig. 1 presents an overview of the CPV-T system installed in Granges, Valais, Switzerland, highlighting its key components, including the triple sun-tracking mirrors, stationary PV-T panel, PLC with its I/O modules, sensors, actuators, and a water tank for thermal energy storage.

A. Hybrid Photovoltaic-thermal Panel and Storage System

The thermal and electrical sub-systems of the stationary PV-T system are shown in Figs. 2, and 3, respectively. The system consists of a photovoltaic-thermal panel with a glass cover and a serpentine tube for efficient heat transfer via circulating water. A water tank stores the thermal energy, while an expansion vessel maintains pressure stability. Fluid circulation is regulated by a pump controlled by a dedicated controller. A cooling system, specifically a heat exchanger, has been implemented to utilize thermal energy as a domestic load. For the electrical sub-system, the PV-T device is connected to a DC/AC converter through a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) device to optimize energy conversion. The key technical specifications of the thermal and electrical sub-systems are presented in Tables I and II, respectively.

B. Remote Data Acquisition, Monitoring and Control Platform

At the core of this setup is a programmable logic controller (PLC), a compact industrial device that enables real-time data acquisition, system monitoring, and precise motor control.

Fig. 2. Hybrid PV system with emphasis on thermal components.

Fig. 3. Hybrid PV system with emphasis on electrical components.

TABLE I
SPECIFICATIONS OF THE COATED DOMESTIC HOT WATER CALORIFIER.

Boiler		Exchanger		
Spec.	Spec.	Spec.	Spec.	Spec.
Volume (L)	Weight (Kg)	Exchanger Surface (m ²)	Max F_L ($\frac{m^3}{h}$)	Min F_L ($\frac{m^3}{h}$)
148	49	0.6	2	1

TABLE II
SPECIFICATIONS OF THE ELECTRICAL PART.

Cell No.	$S_{I_{STC}}$ ($\frac{W}{m^2}$)	T_{STC} ($^{\circ}C$)	V_{oc} (V)	I_{sc} (A)	$P_{E_{mpp}}$ (W)	$P_{T_{nom}}$ (W)
60	1000	25	38.5	8.15	250	350

The PLC interfaces with I/O modules to collect and process data from temperature sensors, flow meters, voltage, current and solar irradiance. It also governs the dual axis tracking mechanism, ensuring accurate and continuous adjustments to optimize solar concentration. As seen in Fig. 4, the PLC is connected to HOOC Gateways, enabling secure remote access and communication. Node-RED ensures seamless data transfer to InfluxDB, enhancing processing capabilities while maintaining secure database access. Integrated with InfluxDB, Grafana offers an intuitive web-based interface for real-time data visualization and efficient data management.

C. Triple Sun-tracker Mirrors

The studied solar tracking system features dual-axis movable mirrors designed to accurately follow the sun's trajectory both daily and seasonally. As shown in Fig. 5, the mirrors and the PV-T system have identical lengths, denoted as L . The distance between the centers of the mirrors, designated as D ,

Fig. 4. Remote data acquisition and monitoring platform.

Fig. 5. Schematic of the studied CPV-T system including the triple sun-tracking mirrors: (a) plan, and (b) sun tracking system operation views.

is maintained as a constant parameter throughout the study. In contrast, the parameter F , which represents the separation between the mirrors and the solar panel, is adjustable. This adjustability is achieved by repositioning either the mirrors or the solar panel, allowing for variations in the experimental setup. For the purposes of this study, the dimensions L , D , and F are standardized to 1 m, 1.5 m, and 10 m, respectively.

Shadow-casting calculations were conducted for various scenarios to analyze the interactions between adjacent mirrors throughout the day, as illustrated in Fig. 6. Until noon, the analysis focused on the shadow cast by the left mirror onto the central mirror and by the central mirror onto the right mirror. From noon until nightfall, the calculations were adjusted to consider the shadow cast by the right mirror onto the central mirror and by the central mirror onto the left mirror. This investigation identified three distinct shadowing scenarios:

- The shadow falls below the mirror's surface. This scenario is common during the morning and evening hours.
- The shadow precisely intersects the midpoint of the mirror. This phenomenon results from variations in the mirrors' inclination angles relative to the sun's position and typically occurs at sunrise and sunset.
- The shadow extends beyond the mirror's surface. This situation is rare and occurs only under extreme conditions, such as when the sun's trajectory shifts significantly northward during the summer months.

Based on the preceding discussion, the concentration curves resulting from the reflection of sunlight by three mirrors onto a PV-T system are illustrated in Fig. 7. These curves,

Fig. 6. Shadow-casting illustration of the CPV-T with three mirrors of the same size as the solar panel.

Fig. 7. Monthly concentration curves from 8 AM to 5 PM, for the CPV-T infrastructure installed in Granges, Valais, Switzerland.

which vary across different months due to the geographical location (Granges, Valais, Switzerland), represent the concentration model of the mirrors focusing sunlight onto the panel. The normal irradiance in the configuration where three sun-tracking mirrors direct sunlight onto the PV-T panel must be adjusted in accordance with these curves to account for temporal variations throughout the day and across different months of the year.

III. OPEN-LOOP CONTROLLER

To effectively direct sunlight onto the PV-T panel, it is crucial to determine the mirror's azimuth and elevation angles, denoted as δ_a and δ_e , respectively, as shown in Fig. 8. Based on this figure, the normal mirror vector can be expressed in a three-dimensional Cartesian form (x , y , and z) in an averaged calculation, where the subscript $(\cdot)_1$ denotes the Cartesian representation of the solar angle:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= \cos(\alpha_S) \cos(-\gamma_S) \\ y_1 &= \cos(\alpha_S) \sin(-\gamma_S) \\ z_1 &= \sin(\alpha_S) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the same format is dominant that the subscript $(\cdot)_2$ denotes the Cartesian-coordinated form of the PV angle:

$$\begin{aligned} x_2 &= \cos(\alpha_T) \cos(-\gamma_T) \\ y_2 &= \cos(\alpha_T) \sin(-\gamma_T) \\ z_2 &= \sin(\alpha_T) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In (1) and (2), α and γ denotes the azimuth and elevation angles, respectively, and subscripts S and T denote the sun and PV angles. Therefore, the normal mirror vector based on three-dimensional Cartesian form (x , y , z) is given in (3):

Fig. 8. Central mirror schematic (a) azimuth, and (b) elevation angles.

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{x_1 - x_2}{2} + x_2 \\ y &= \frac{y_1 - y_2}{2} + y_2 \\ z &= \frac{z_1 - z_2}{2} + z_2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The mirror's azimuth and elevation angles δ_a and δ_e can be calculated using trigonometric principles as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_a &= \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \right) \\ \delta_e &= \begin{cases} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{-y}{x} \right) & \text{if } x > 0 \\ \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{-y}{x} \right) + 90 & \text{if } x < 0, \text{ and } y \geq 0 \\ \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{-y}{x} \right) - 90 & \text{if } x < 0, \text{ and } y < 0 \\ 90 & \text{if } x = 0, \text{ and } y > 0 \\ -90 & \text{if } x = 0, \text{ and } y < 0 \\ \text{undefined} & \text{if } x = 0, \text{ and } y = 0 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Since linear motors are used to orient the mirrors, the setpoint position in millimeters is required for both motors. The azimuth motor operates within a setpoint range of 0 to 300 mm, while the altitude motor ranges from 0 to 150 mm. By correlating the mirror angles with the motor positions, a 3-D model of the mirror system is utilized to accurately establish this relationship. The relationship between the mirror angles and the motors' linear positions is determined using the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} W_a &= 7.234e^{-7} \delta_a^4 + 0.0001396 \delta_a^3 - 0.008193 \delta_a^2 \\ &\quad - 3.607 \delta_a + 161.9 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_e &= -0.0001746 \delta_e^3 + 0.006216 \delta_e^2 + 4.255 \delta_e \\ &\quad - 2.028 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where W_a and W_e represent the linear positions of the azimuth and elevation motors, respectively, in millimeters. The implementation of the open-loop controller can be illustrated using a block diagram system, as shown in Fig. 9, which is segmented into four main components:

- The first block calculates the sun's position (azimuth angle α_s and elevation angle γ_s) at a specific location

Fig. 9. Open-loop controller structure.

Fig. 10. Recorded climatic data of the studied site for January & February, 2025 data: (a) irradiance, and (b) ambient temperature.

and time using the solar position algorithm (SPA), which is a toolbox within the applied PLC.

- The second block converts these solar angles into corresponding mirror angles (δ_a and δ_e), using equations (1) to (5).
- The third block translates the mirror angles into setpoints for the two linear motors (see (6) and (7)).
- The final block provides closed-loop control, including position, velocity, and current controllers for the motor positions.

Note that a limitation of this method is the potential misalignment of the coaxial mirrors due to mechanical constraints and uncertainties in the system parameters of the studied setup.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of the studied system and its components, as described in Section II. The system is controlled by an open-loop controller, as detailed in Section III, for dual-axis sun-tracking mirrors. Under standard test conditions (STC), the nominal thermal power of the system is 350 W, while the nominal electrical power is 250 W (see Table II).

Fig. 10 presents the climatic data including irradiance, Irr , and ambient temperature, T_{Amb} , of the studied site for January & February, 2025. By employing the open-loop controller outlined in Section III, the corresponding results are presented in Fig. 11. As illustrated in the figure, the output thermal power consistently attains or exceeds the nominal power across the majority of the specified time intervals. This observation underscores the efficacy of the proposed approach in achieving the desired performance metrics.

To evaluate the efficacy of the proposed method, the input and output data for each time interval are systematically

Fig. 11. Recorded thermal power data of the studied site for January & February, 2025 data using the open-loop controller.

Fig. 12. The moving-average plot of the recorded data.

Fig. 13. Heat-map plot of the averaged inputs and outputs for January & February, 2025 data using the open-loop controller.

averaged and normalized. The results depicted in Fig. 12 demonstrate that the reflection of solar radiation by the mirrors exerts the most significant influence. This is corroborated by the direct correlation observed across both sub-figures in Fig. 12. To further elucidate this phenomenon, a heat map is presented in Fig. 13. The symmetry of the heat map, with its axis of symmetry aligned at 100% (i.e., a normalized value of 1), clearly indicates that the reflection efficiency of the mirrors is the predominant factor in determining the output thermal power generation. This finding underscores the critical role of mirror reflectivity in optimizing system performance. Fig. 14 shows the electrical power output on February 13, 2025, reaching a saturation level of 250 W around 2 PM before gradually decreasing due to the electrical load.

Preliminary field testing of the CPV-T system under real-world conditions demonstrated the following:

- Efficient solar tracking: The controlled dual-axis tracking system accurately followed the sun's movement, ensuring

Fig. 14. The electrical power for February 13, 2025 data using the open-loop controller.

maximum solar concentration on the PV-T module.

- Enhanced energy generation: Real-time data confirmed significant improvements, with the thermal power output of the CPV-T system increasing 3.2 times compared to the fixed PV-T system under the same conditions, while the electrical power output reached saturation, highlighting the benefits of the active solar tracking mechanism.
- Enhancing efficiency and reliability in mirror-aligned CPV-T system: Achieving precise and continuous alignment of mirrors with the sun's trajectory presents a significant challenge, as any latency or misalignment can diminish energy capture efficiency. To address this, advanced motor control algorithms can be optimized to improve real-time responsiveness and minimize tracking errors. Integrating machine learning with classical control principles offers a scalable framework for enhancing CPV-T performance, with implications for industrial solar cogeneration systems seeking robust, adaptive energy harvesting [17], [18].

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of a dual-axis mirror-integrated solar tracking system in enhancing the performance of a concentrated photovoltaic-thermal (CPV-T) system. The proposed design, utilizing three dynamically adjustable mirrors and an open-loop controller, significantly improves thermal and electrical efficiency. Experimental results show a threefold increase in thermal power output compared to fixed systems, with electrical power reaching saturation levels. However, challenges such as mechanical limitations, mirror misalignment, and parameter uncertainties remain. Future work should explore adaptive control algorithms, advanced optical coatings, and system scalability for industrial applications. Addressing these issues will advance CPV-T technology, contributing to more efficient and sustainable solar energy systems.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Sioshansi and P. Denholm, "The value of concentrating solar power and thermal energy storage," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 173–183, 2010.
- [2] A. Bahrami, C. O. Okoye, and U. Atikol, "Technical and economic assessment of fixed, single and dual-axis tracking pv panels in low latitude countries," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 113, pp. 563–579, 2017.
- [3] K. Moradi, F. Jafari, F. Moghaddam, and Q. Shafiee, "Modeling of photovoltaic-thermal systems using multivariate polynomial regression," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 136–143, 2024.
- [4] F. Jafari, K. Moradi, Q. Shafiee, and F. Moghaddam, "Data-driven performance modeling of solar panels using polynomial regression," in *2024 International Conference on Control, Automation and Diagnosis (ICCAD)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–8.
- [5] M. A. Ceballos, Á. Valera, P. Sanmartín, F. Almonacid, and E. F. Fernández, "Development and indoor characterization of a concentrator photovoltaic assembly for tracking-integrated systems," *Solar Energy*, vol. 255, pp. 292–300, 2023.
- [6] M. Burhan, S. J. Oh, K. J. E. Chua, and K. C. Ng, "Double lens collimator solar feedback sensor and master slave configuration: Development of compact and low cost two axis solar tracking system for cpv applications," *Solar Energy*, vol. 137, pp. 352–363, 2016.
- [7] M. A. Ceballos, P. J. Pérez-Higueras, E. F. Fernández, and F. Almonacid, "Tracking-integrated cpv technology: State-of-the-art and classification," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 15, p. 5605, 2023.
- [8] A. Khouya, "Performance assessment of a heat pump and a concentrated photovoltaic thermal system during the wood drying process," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 180, p. 115923, 2020.
- [9] M. I. Hussain and G. H. Lee, "Experimental and numerical studies of a u-shaped solar energy collector to track the maximum cpvt system output by varying the flow rate," *Renewable energy*, vol. 76, pp. 735–742, 2015.
- [10] F. Jafari, K. Moradi, and Q. Shafiee, "Shallow learning vs. deep learning in engineering applications," in *Shallow Learning vs. Deep Learning: A Practical Guide for Machine Learning Solutions*. Springer, 2024, pp. 29–76.
- [11] M. K. Kalamroudi, M. Ilkan, F. Egelioglu, and B. Safaei, "Maximization of the output power of low concentrating photovoltaic systems by the application of reflecting mirrors," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 189, pp. 822–835, 2022.
- [12] V. Badescu, "Theoretical derivation of heliostat tracking errors distribution," *Solar energy*, vol. 82, no. 12, pp. 1192–1197, 2008.
- [13] K. Aiuchi, K. Yoshida, M. Onozaki, Y. Katayama, M. Nakamura, and K. Nakamura, "Sensor-controlled heliostat with an equatorial mount," *Solar Energy*, vol. 80, no. 9, pp. 1089–1097, 2006.
- [14] Y. Chen, K. Chong, B. Lim, and C. Lim, "Study of residual aberration for non-imaging focusing heliostat," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 79, no. 1, pp. 1–20, 2003.
- [15] C. E. Moeller, T. D. Brumleve, C. Grosskreutz, and L. O. Seamons, "Central receiver test facility albuquerque, new mexico," *Solar Energy*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 291–302, 1980.
- [16] A. Kribus, I. Vishnevsky, A. Yogeve, and T. Rubinov, "Closed loop control of heliostats," *Energy*, vol. 29, no. 5-6, pp. 905–913, 2004.
- [17] K. Moradi, F. Jafari, F. Moghaddam, and Q. Shafiee, "Dynamic modeling of photovoltaic-thermal systems using polynomial regression," *Available at SSRN 5047736*.
- [18] —, "Optimizing efficiency in concentrated photovoltaic-thermal systems by solar tracking mirrors," *Available at SSRN 5059205*.